

HUMAN-CENTRIC AI-ENABLED EXTENDED REALITY APPLICATIONS FOR THE
INDUSTRY 5.0 ERA

D7.2 – DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION,
STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Definition
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDA	Attention Interest Desire Action
AIOTI	Alliance for IoT Innovation
AITI	Associazione Industrie Ticinesi
AR	Augmented Reality
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CEN/ CENELEC	European Committee for Standardization /European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CES	Consumer Electronics Show
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CTA	Call to Action
DAIRO	Data Artificial Intelligence and Robotics
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoA	Description of Action
DTs	Digital Twins
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
EIRA	European Interoperability Reference Architecture
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
ERCIM	European Research Consortium for Informatics and Mathematics
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IEEE	Institute of Electric and Electronic Engineers
IIRA	Industrial Internet Reference Architecture
INDIN	IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IVRAM	Industrial Value Chain Reference Architecture
I5.0	Industry 5.0

KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LASFA	LAsim Smart Factory
MR	Mixed Reality
OA	Open Access
OMG	Object Management Group
ONNX	Open Neural Network Exchange
RAMI	Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0
ROI	Return on Investment
SDOs	Standards Development Organizations
SITAM	Stuttgart IT-Architecture for Manufacturing
TBA	To Be Announced
TOC	Table of Contents
TOGAF	The Open Group Architectural Framework
UC	Use Case
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VR	Virtual Reality
VRIF	Virtual Reality Industry Forum
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
XR	Extended Reality

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on the dissemination and communication activities of the first year of the XR5.0 Horizon Europe project's lifetime. It is released at M12 of the XR5.0 workplan and is the project's first official report on "Dissemination, Communication, Standardisation Activities. Two similar reports will be produced and released at the end of the next two years of the project i.e. at M24 and M36 of the project.

The XR5.0 project develops, demonstrates, and validates an innovative Person-Centric AI-based paradigm for industrial XR applications that exhibit Industry 5.0 characteristics. Specifically, the project focuses on providing innovative "XR-made-in-Europe" technologies that foster the development and integration of industrial XR applications with human-centric manufacturing technologies, including trustworthy AI technologies and technologies that enable human-AI collaboration. In this context, one of the main objectives of the project is to develop a vibrant ecosystem (XR5.0-Ecosystem) of interested and engaged stakeholders around the project's results, including a community of manufacturers, providers of industrial automation solutions, Industry 5.0 and AI researchers, as well as policymakers and Standards Development Organizations (SDOs). The main goal of the project's dissemination activities described in this deliverable is to raise awareness about the project's outcomes towards relevant stakeholders, to engage these stakeholders with the project's outcomes and to build the project's community. This deliverable focuses on the activities of the first year, building on the dissemination and communication plan that has been presented in an earlier deliverable of X5.0, namely D7.1.

The deliverable presents the project's accomplishments in different areas of dissemination activities, including scientific and non-scientific publications, participation in conferences and workshops, as well as publication of results through social and electronic media. The density of these activities is in line with the overall flow and pace of production of the project's outcomes. In this respect, during the first year of the project, XR5.0 has paid emphasis on establishing and growing the project's community through digital and electronic channels, while some other activities (e.g., publications) have progressed at a rather slower pace as they need to be fed by mature scientific results. During the second year of the project, the dissemination activities will intensify at all fronts, given the constant and intensified flow of the project's scientific and industrial results.

One of the main highlights of the activities of the reporting period has been the establishment of a cluster of EU-funded XR projects, which was established with XR5.0 in a leading role. Specifically, XR5.0 has taken the initiative to contact relevant XR projects (notably project focusing on industrial use cases) in order to plan joint dissemination and communication activities with them towards maximizing their impact. XR5.0 has led the organization of two joint webinars (i.e. thematic webinars with contributions from different projects of the cluster) during 2024, while planning additional webinars for 2025. All webinars received considerable interest from the community and were joined by 100s of participants.

Emphasis has been also paid during the period on growing and keeping track of the project's community in terms of profile and interested stakeholders in the project's results. In this direction, XR5.0 is maintaining and keeping up to date a stakeholders' database, which includes people and organisation that have interacted with XR5.0 through different channels and touch points. Likewise, the project is consistently and continually tracking KPIs, including how they compare to the project's pledges listed in the XR5.0 Grant Agreement.

The deliverable provides insights on the planning of the dissemination and communication activities of the second year of the project, which are also presented in the document herein, considering the second year's KPIs. The purpose of the planning is to ensure that the project KPIs are achieved and that the necessary actions are taken to fine-tune the dissemination strategy towards meeting the project's goals and maximising the impact of the project's outcomes.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope and Purpose

The aim of this deliverable is to present and analyse all the dissemination, communications and standardisation activities that have been concluded during the project's first year and is the first one of the deliverable series "Dissemination, Communication, Standardisation Activities." One of the main objectives of the XR5.0 project is to develop a vibrant ecosystem of interested and committed stakeholders around the project's results. Thus, as analysed in the previous – first deliverable, "Dissemination and Community Building Plan," a specific methodology named AIDA (Attention Interest Desire Action) has been adopted to reach the KPIs fully analysed in DoA. According to this methodology, the priority is raising project awareness among related communities and stakeholders. Thus, the dissemination channels constantly upload updates regarding the project's news and achievements. The goal is to create a vibrant community about XR, including relevant stakeholders, manufacturers, industrial organisations, integrators of Industry 5.0 solutions, AI experts, Industry 5.0 / XR and AI researchers, SDOs, policymakers, regulators and more. During XR5.0 second year, all the dissemination activities will aim at generative interest for stakeholders to engage with the project through presenting technological achievements and use cases with industrial value and potential Return on Investment (ROI). In this last phase – the project's last year, the dissemination and communication activities will primarily target the actual engagement of stakeholders with the project's results based on the dissemination of CTA (Call for Action) and the provision of relevant incentives (e.g., access to premium content and demonstrators).

Apart from the presentation and analysis of the accomplished dissemination and communication activities, the deliverable includes planning for next year's activities. The rationale behind reporting the plan for the second year's activities is to ensure that that dissemination strategy is updated to incorporate feedback from the actual implementation of the activities that have been accomplished, but also to ensure that the targeted KPIs (including the targets listed in the project's DoA) are met.

The list of dissemination activities and artifacts that are presented in the deliverable include:

- The branded dissemination and communication materials were created and used in the project. These materials have already been presented in earlier deliverable D7.1. The present deliverable includes new material that has been created following the delivery of D7.1, such as flyers about the project's pilots and banners about the webinars organized by the project.
- The electronic communication channels (including social media channels) that the project has established and is using to provide its updates and dissemination information. The deliverable presents information about the use of these channels, including information about the performed posts social media metrics and statistics that indicate the performance and impact of these channels.
- The scientific papers and other publications that have been produced in the first year of the project.
- Dissemination events (e.g., workshops, conferences) in which the XR5.0 partners have participated or organised.
- The project's synergies with other XR projects (notably EU-funded projects), including joint activities that have been led by XR5.0 such as two webinars that have taken place during the project.
- The establishment, analysis and maintenance of the project's stakeholder database.
- Additional XR5.0 activities concerning collaboration and liaisons with SDOs and industrial organisations.

1.2 Deliverable Structure

The remainder of the deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 2**, following this introductory section, showcases the branding processes that have been done, including logo creation, specific templates that partners use, and the creation of flyers, including pilots' information. Some of the elements of the branding process were also presented in the previous deliverable, yet they are updated in this deliverable based on information about pilot flyers and the banners' used in webinars.

- **Section 3** provides information about the website statistics and presents the results of social media and Newsletters that the project achieved during the first year. Meanwhile, a presentation of the blog posts that partners have written is provided.
- **Section 4** presents the scientific publications published during the first year. In addition, any activities that partners have done are also showcased. The chapter ends with a plan for the next scientific publication of partners.
- **Section 5** analyse the XR synergies that have been achieved during the first year of the project. A presentation of the monthly meetings, the webinars, and the plan for the next year is also underlined.
- **Section 6** presents the database of the XR5.0 project and analyses the demographic characteristics.
- **Section 7** provides information about the project's activities and contributions to industrial associations, project clusters, and SDOs.
- **Section 8** is the final chapter of the deliverable. This section provides a summary and a critical assessment of the first year's dissemination, communications and standardisation activities.

2. XR5.0 BRAND IDENTIFY

2.1 XR5.0 Logo

Creating the project’s logo is the key element in its communication. The XR5.0 logo provides a visual depiction of the project and helps to establish the brand's identity. To make the project name immediately recognisable to everybody, XR5.0 incorporates it within the logo, using distinct colours. The rationale behind the creation of the XR5.0 brand was to design a wordmark, where the logo and the icon merge and create a unique and modern logotype. This way, the typography represents not only the name of the project but also the virtual world through the virtual reality glasses see Figure 1.

Figure 1- The Official Logo of the XR5.0 Project

In constructing this wordmark, the spacing was carefully considered, allowing the logo to be used alongside other logos while still standing out. The colour versions show the many combinations the logo allows and the correct use of each option (as shown in Figure 2).

Figure 2-Size and Different Versions of the XR5.0 logo.

During the initial two months of the project, five distinct visuals of the logo were developed in collaboration with creative experts, as illustrated in the accompanying Figure 3. This process was aimed to provide several creation options to the partners as part of a “logo selection process”.

Figure 3 – XR5.0 Logo Options that Drove the Logo Selection Process

A specialised poll was conducted to assess the reception of five new logo visuals alongside the logo crafted for the proposal (see Figure 4). Following this process, the logo featured during the proposal phase emerged as the preferred choice among most partners.

Figure 4 – The Poll of the XR5.0 Logo Selection Process

2.2 XR5.0 Branding Materials

Creating a specific stand out from similar projects is important. Acknowledging this, XR5.0 aimed at establishing a specific brand material to be used by the project. At first, the colour palette of the project’s visuals is similar to the purple tones of the logo’s colours. Both the look and feel of the website (see Figure 5) and the visuals on social media (Figure 6) are based on the specific colour palette.

Figure 5 – XR5.0 Website look and feel

Figure 6 – Sample XR5.0 Social Media Layout

2.3 Templates

Establishing the project's brand identity includes creating templates for its documents and presentations. The following elements are part of the document template set:

- Figure 7 illustrates the Deliverable Template, which also serves as a basis for the layout of other project documents like press releases and white papers.
- Figure 8, illustrates the Presentation Template, which is used by project members in all project presentations including internal presentations (e.g., in project meetings) and presentations to third parties (e.g., during dissemination events).

XR5.0
HUMAN-CENTRIC AI-ENABLED EXTENDED REALITY APPLICATIONS FOR THE
INDUSTRY 5.0 ERA

DX.Y – TITLE OF THE DELIVERABLE

Lead Beneficiary	Partner Acronym
Work Package Ref.	WPX – Reference Work package Name
Task Ref.	TX.Z – Reference Task Name
Deliverable Title	DX.Y – Title of the Deliverable
Due Date	yyyy-mm-dd
Delivered Date	yyyy-mm-dd
Revision Number	M.N.
Dissemination Level	Public (PU) or Confidential (CO)
Type	Report (R) or Other (ORDP) or ETHICS
Document Status	Draft or Release
Review Status	Internally Reviewed and/or Quality Assurance Reviewed
Document Acceptance	WP Leader Accepted and/or Coordinator Accepted
EC Project Officer	Ms. Tunde LEVY

Figure 7 – Snapshot of the XR5.0. Deliverable Template.

Figure 8 – Snapshot of the XR5.0 Presentation Template.

2.4 Pilot Flyers and Banners

2.4.1 Pilot Flyers

Different flyers were created for the six (6) pilots of the project, given that the pilots are among the main technical results of the project and are like to be among the main exploitable outcomes of the project with clear commercial relevance. The flyers aim to visualise all the areas that pilots should point out. Thus, the following points/content are included in each pilot:

- Information about the Use cases that are comprised by the pilot.
- Users/ Personas relevant to the pilot systems.
- Application(s) relevant to the pilot.
- Research Areas that relate to the pilot.
- A mini description of the pilot.
- Technologies used in the pilot (including XR5.0 technologies).
- Solutions relevant to the pilot system.

The project and its partners are distributing these flyers to increase their visibility. The design follows a carefully selected colour palette consistent with the project's graphic visuals. To differentiate the flyers for each pilot, a unique colour has been incorporated in the centre of each flyer, making it easy to distinguish them from one another (see Figure 9). Additionally, a QR code has been added to each pilot, and a call to action to scan and read more on the website has been added, too.

Figure 9-Overview of the Flyers of the Six (6) XR5.0 pilots.

2.4.2 Banners

Multiple banners have been designed for use across various communication channels, including social media platforms, the project website, and newsletters. During the first year of the project, two webinars were conducted in collaboration with other XR-related initiatives. To promote these events, dedicated banners were created featuring all relevant details along with the logos of the participating projects. These banners were published on the XR5.0 website and social media platforms and shared with the XR cluster for dissemination through their respective channels, further amplifying outreach and visibility (see Figure 10, Figure 11).

Figure 10- Social Media Visual of the 1st Webinar of the XR Projects Cluster (organized by XR5.0).

Figure 11- Social Media Visual of the 2nd Webinar of the XR Projects Cluster (organized by XR5.0).

3. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

3.1 Website

3.1.1 Website Overview

The homepage of the website of XR5.0 describes what the project is about, presents the latest news of the project, provides information about the synergies about the XR community that have been made, and includes links to the project’s social media channels: Facebook, X, LinkedIn, and YouTube (see Figure 12). Between M3 and M12, the website has constantly expanded in terms of content categories and updated in terms of content. Each pilot has a pilot section with a landing page and an individual page, where pilot-specific information is and will be published. There is also a resources section containing all important public resources of the project, including videos, deliverables, publications, a communications kit, and newsletters. There is also a separate “News” section, namely the “News Hub”, that includes project news, events, and blog posts. The blog post category is updated with partners’ blog posts every month (see Figure 13).

Information about the XR5.0 Consortium is also included on the website. A dedicated webpage provides all the necessary contact information if any user needs clarifications, information or wants to communicate with the project.

Figure 12- XR5.0 Website homepage

Figure 13- XR5.0 Blog posts' Webpage

3.1.2 Website Analytics

Google Analytics was set up on the XR5.0 website during M3. Various insights regarding the users' behavior are provided in Figure 14 .

Figure 14- XR5.0 Website statistics based on Google Analytics

Since the project’s beginning, **1.6K users have been launched on the XR5.0 website**. The most visited webpage is the project’s homepage; the second is the consortium page, and the blog webpage follows. Interestingly, a specific blog post named “Extended Reality (XR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) Integration: Five Industrial Cases you need to know”, which was the first one that was published on the website, has gained a lot of users’ views (239 views).

3.2 Social Media

Social media is one of the most effective tools to disseminate a project's achievements and activities to users. Thus, a specific strategy has been established, including continuous posting, with approximately **4-6 posts original posts per month**. In addition, each month XR5.0 reposts content from relevant posts and social media synergies.

The project aims to establish a community and create a network using social media platforms. It is also vital to regularly engage with stakeholders, connect with relevant accounts, and promote regular news about the XR5.0 project and events that XR5.0 is attending or organizing. Disseminating the project's outcomes and updates is also essential.

In the first year, some relevant hashtags and topics were available for users to interact with on both social media channels. The goal was to increase reach and awareness while building upon a strong presence in these channels.

The dedicated hashtags which were used are the following: #XRTechnology #ExtendedReality #XR50. Additional relevant hashtags are added to each post.

 : <https://www.linkedin.com/company/xr5-0-project/>

 : <https://x.com/XR50project>

 : <https://tinyurl.com/yeydc2df>

 : <https://tinyurl.com/4dydeeph>

Social media were updated regularly to increase awareness and engagement in these communities. A fresh graphic with a specific layout suitable for the platform accompanies all social media posts for the purpose of each post. Additionally, every post uses the XR5.0 logo, as promoting branding awareness is vital for the project. In addition, every post has a text with an appealing call to action (CTA), which guides users to relevant material on the XR5.0 website. Social media posts generally point to news articles, events or publications on the XR5.0 website.

3.2.1 LinkedIn

The XR5.0 Project's LinkedIn account was launched at the beginning of M1 to promote and showcase the project's achievements. It serves as a key platform to increase awareness among the target audience, spark interest, and attract participants to XR5.0 webinars/ events. The account also aims to cultivate a vibrant and engaged community, fostering knowledge exchange and building an ecosystem that drives innovation and advances the XR industry.

As Figure 15 displays, the LinkedIn page of the project has **358 followers** (as of December 8th, 2024). During the first year, the initial strategy set a baseline of at least **two monthly posts**. However, in practice, a significantly higher posting frequency has been adopted. Specifically, **approximately 4-6 posts** related to the project are published monthly. Some reposts of relevant projects or reposts that mention the XR5.0

project are also being published on the LinkedIn page. The total LinkedIn posts and reposts excluded from the first year were 55.

Figure 15 - LinkedIn page and followers

The main content of the LinkedIn page includes posts that announce an event/conference, webinars, significant achievements of partners like workshops or publications, blog posts of the consortium, posts from project synergies, and other relevant reposts (see Figure 16, Figure 17).

The XR5.0 LinkedIn page is also being enhanced with publishing in LinkedIn groups that are relevant to the XR community, such as [Artificial Intelligence Investors Group: Robotics, Machine Learning, NLP, Computer Vision & IoT, Reality Innovators Network for Spatial Computing, Metaverse, AI & XR - Virtual, Augmented Reality](#).

Furthermore, relevant hashtags have been created to enhance the organic content of the LinkedIn page: **#XR50project #euproject #ai #extendedreality #europeanprojects #horizoneu**

Apart from posts produced by the project’s dissemination team, the channels of the project and the project’s achievements are frequently referenced and included within personal posts of the XR5.0 project members and posts of related projects (e.g., projects of the XR projects cluster) as indicated in Annex II. These additional posts reinforce the project’s LinkedIn account and increase its outreach.

Figure 16-Sample LinkedIn posts of XR5.0

Figure 17- Sample of LinkedIn repost.

In terms of LinkedIn statistics (depicted in Figure 18), there is a number of 25,343 impressions that indicate how many times the post has been seen and a number (968) of reactions to the posts that demonstrate the overall engagement of the community with the XR5.0 posts. The posts have been reposted 57 times, and 21 comments have been made. Focusing more on the XR5.0 followers, 14.3% are occupied in Business Development, 11% are from education, 10% are engineers and 9.5% are researchers.

Figure 18-LinkedIn Statistics.

Table 1 displays some of the posts that gained more than 1,000 impressions (until the end of November 2024) during the project’s first year.

Table 1-LinkedIn posts with more than 1,000 Impressions.

N0.	Link	Visual	Impressions
1	https://tinyurl.com/52j58sdf	A poster for the XR5.0 'Kick of meeting' held in Milan, Italy, on February 20-21, 2024. The image shows a group of people in a meeting room.	1,478
2	https://tinyurl.com/8er7a46z	A poster titled 'Personalizing XR Applications and Human-Robot Interaction with Digital Twins'. It features a person wearing a VR headset in a futuristic, blue-toned environment.	1,148
3	https://tinyurl.com/4wrzzdw7	A poster announcing the '#1 Press Release is out!'. It features a stylized robot head and the XR5.0 logo. A small text at the bottom states: 'The XR5.0 project received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grants Agreement no. 101135209'.	1,041

4	https://tinyurl.com/45fxe29z		1,224
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3.2.2 X

The X account of XR5.0 was established in the project's first year. Currently (December 8th, 2024), the account has 34 unique followers; as depicted in Figure 19, 184 posts have been shared, including the retweets.

Figure 19-X project's account

The XR5.0 account on X employs a targeted strategy to publish engaging content while actively engaging with the XR community. This involves retweeting two relevant posts weekly to amplify the project's visibility and foster connections within the broader XR ecosystem.

This approach helps the account steadily grow its community and enables the project to identify and engage with other relevant initiatives or stakeholders that may hold potential value for collaboration or knowledge exchange. Additionally, the XR5.0 account actively follows similar projects to stay updated on industry trends and maintain alignment with related efforts.

The X account is successfully meeting its KPIs, posting more than two times a month according to the strategic goals. The content strategy for the X account closely aligns with that of LinkedIn, ensuring consistency across platforms. However, all posts are adapted before being published on X to align with the platform's unique tone and text format. Frequent retweets significantly enhance the project's visibility, broadening its reach and engagement within the XR and VR communities.

Figure 20 – Sample XR5.0 posts on the X platform

Figure 21 – Sample repost of an XR5.0 post.

3.2.3 Facebook

Aligned with its broader social media strategy, XR5.0 maintains an active presence on Facebook by publishing 4-6 posts per month. These posts aim to inform, engage, and foster connections with their target audience. Additionally, to maximise visibility and participation in XR5.0 webinars, dedicated "events" are created on the platform, serving as an effective tool to attract a wider audience (see Figure 22). Note, however, that XR5.0 does not consider Facebook as its primary and focal channel, but rather a secondary, auxiliary communication channels that aims to complement the outreach achieved through LinkedIn and X.

Figure 22 – XR5.0 Facebook Account

3.2.4 YouTube

The YouTube channel is vital to the project's dissemination and communication strategy. Thus, as the project concludes its first year, four videos have been published on the channel (see Figure 23). By the end of the project, more than ten videos should be uploaded, with several categories included: workshops, webinars, tutorials, etc. The content includes videos from the Kick-off Meeting, the first general assembly meeting, and the two cluster webinars conducted during the project's first year. The total number of views the YouTube channel has gained until the end of November is 280.

Figure 23- XR5.0 YouTube Account

3.3 Newsletters

Newsletters aim to raise awareness and share relevant and valuable information and results to the XR5.0 mailing list. They also aim to keep stakeholders informed on topics such as new blog posts, upcoming events, and any other relevant updates related to the project. XR5.0 Project boosts the visibility of the newsletter sign-up through a relevant banner on the homepage of the project’s website. Specifically, the newsletter sign-up is visible on the website’s footer to ensure anyone can register when they want. Targeted social media posts are also crafted to include a compelling call to action, which includes encouraging users to subscribe to the XR5.0 Newsletters to enhance the relevant mailing list / list of recipients for the project’s newsletter.

The newsletters have similar interfaces regarding the colors used to create a brand identity. Regarding Newsletters’ content, the main goal is to inform the relevant list regarding the latest news of the project, the synergies made and the release of the partners’ blog posts. Until M12 (December 2024), XR5.0 has produced and sent 4 Newsletters to the relevant mailing list. The latter has already 127 members who are relevant to the project. According to the KPI for Newsletters, by December 2024 the goal was to produce and dispatch at least two newsletters the first year.

Table 2 below displays the four newsletters sent during the project's first year. As statistics show, the newsletter about the first cluster webinar gained the most clicks per unique opens.

Table 2- XR5.0 Newsletters Produced and Dispatched during the Reporting Period (Jan-Dec 2024)

NL - Date	Newsletters Interface	Link	Successful Deliveries	Clicks per Unique Opens
<p>1st – May 24, 2024</p>		<p>Click here to see the 1st the Newsletter</p>	<p>109</p>	<p>17,78%</p>
<p>2nd – July 25, 2024</p>		<p>Click here to see 2nd Newsletter</p>	<p>113</p>	<p>13,89%</p>

<p>3rd – September 3, 2024</p>		<p>Click here to see 3rd Newsletter</p>	<p>115</p>	<p>20%</p>
<p>4th – September 9, 2024</p>		<p>Click here to see 4th Newsletter</p>	<p>116</p>	<p>9,52%</p>

3.4 Published Blog Posts

XR5.0 has put emphasis on the production of informative blog posts. All partners have engaged in the production/authoring of blog posts, which are published on the project’s web site and promoted through social media. This increased the overall visibility of the project, while at the same time providing the XR5.0 partners with opportunities to promote their own work and their unique contributions to the project. Within the first year, XR5.0 has met the targeted blog production/publication KPI, which was to publish two blog posts per month, considering however that the regular publication of blog posts started effectively in March 2024. Nineteen (19) blog posts have been published and received many thousands of views/impressions on the project’s social media. Annex III summarises the blog posts published on the project website and its social media channels. The in Annex III list reflects the partners’ collaborative effort in producing blog posts regularly.

3.5 Projects Announcements – Local Level Dissemination

XR5.0 has produced announcements about some of the project’s milestones on the official website of the project. As illustrated in Annex I, these announcements were also posted on the partners’ web sites. In this way, the partners’ followers and stakeholders were informed about XR5.0 and its activities. Likewise, this cross-promotion strategy increased the website traffic. It enhanced the project's credibility by featuring XR5.0 on multiple reputable websites.

Note also that several partners posted announcements and information about XR5.0 at their regions’ level. For instance, the Portuguese partners of XR5.0 produced and posted three XR5.0 announcements in Portuguese newspapers and websites. One of the posts/articles was published in a Portuguese newspaper named “[Público](#)” on Thursday, November 21, 2024. *Público* is primarily a Portuguese newspaper, and it features dedicated sections on science, technology, and related topics, such as “Ciência e Ambiente” (Science and Environment), which could attract industry professionals and enthusiasts. Two more blog posts were published on two Portuguese websites ([Technet.com](#), [Kiosquedaaviacao.pt](#)) that presented the XR5.0 project.

3.6 Future Planning (M13-M24) (January 2025-December 2025)

Table 3 below outlines the project’s plan to achieve and, where possible, exceed the KPIs defined in the DoA about dissemination in social and electronic channels. This plan includes a range of activities, including regular social media updates, website enhancements, newsletters, blog posts featuring content provided by partners, as well as the development of whitepapers and press releases.

Table 3 –Planning of Dissemination and Communication Activities for M13-M24

DoA KPIs for the 2 nd Year	Planning for the 2 nd Year
-Social Media content: >3/month -Blogposts on website: >3/month -Videos, YouTube channel: total in three years >=10	-Social Media content: 5-6/month -Blogposts on website: 3/month -Videos, YouTube channel: 3-4 videos
-Newsletters: Y2: >=4 (1/UC) -Press Releases: Y2: >=4 (1/UC) -White papers: Y2: >3/month	-Newsletters: Y2: >=5-6 -Creation of Press release template to disseminate to partners - A whitepaper template will be created and shared with partners for dissemination. Each pilot partner will use this template to write a relevant whitepaper. Typically, XR5.0 will target the production of at least 1 white paper for each pilot till the end of the project, focusing on the description of solutions with commercial relevance.

4. PUBLICATIONS AND WORKSHOPS

4.1 Overview of Coordination Activities towards Publications and other Activities

As the project's first year draws to a close, various dissemination activities that align with the DoA have been carried out. The dissemination team has created a specific strategy to ensure the project's dissemination activities are well on track. This includes the regular organization of online WP7 meetings in addition to meetings organized during face-to-face events (e.g., the project’s kick-off and general assembly meetings). In principle, WP7 meetings take place at a bi-weekly frequency. The objectives of each meeting are twofold: on the one hand, they are aimed at informing the consortium about the latest updates in each dissemination area, while on the other partners discuss with the dissemination team their planned activities. During 2024, eight of these bi-weekly meetings had a dissemination and communication focus, yet WP7 meetings with exploitation and standardization focus have been organized as well.

4.2 (Open Access) Scientific Publications

As the project's first year draws to a close, various dissemination activities that align with the DoA have been carried out. One of the main goals of these activities is to reach scientific and technical audiences and to engage/on-board relevant stakeholders to the project’s community. Few of these activities were already listed in deliverable D7.1, notably the few activities that took place during the first four months of the project. Table 4 presents the project’s scientific publications (conferences and journals). Currently, one (1) magazine article, four (4) conference papers and one (1) journal publication have been published. Note that the number of publications is in-line with the overall plan of the project for producing scientific publication, which foresees an small number of publications during the first year of the project and increased numbers during the second (i.e., M13-M24) and third (i.e., M25-M36) of the project. This is reasonable given that

publications are generally driven by the production of quite mature results,. The production of mature results will happen after the first year of the project’s lifetime.

All the scientific publications of the project will be available as Open Access in either Green OA or Gold OA mode. The publications listed in Table 4 are generally available as green OA (i.e. a pre-final version of these publications is available through the project’s web site and the project’s space in Zenodo).

Table 4- XR5.0 Scientific publications (M1-M12) (January 2024- December 2025).

NO.	Scientific Publications
1	<p>Magazine - Article "XR5.0: Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era", ERCIM News 137 (May 2024), Special theme: Extended Reality. By John Soldatos, Georgios Makridis, and Fotis Liarokapis Contributing partners: INNOV-ACTS, UPRC, CYENS</p>
2	<p>Journal Publication Mavrogiorgos, K., Kiourtis, A., Mavrogiorgou, A., Menychtas, A., & Kyriazis, D. (2024). Bias in Machine Learning: A Literature Review. <i>Applied Sciences</i>, 14(19), 8860. https://doi.org/10.3390/app14198860 Contributing partner: UPRC</p>
3	<p>Conference Paper 'Impact of Collaborative Robots on Human Trust, Anxiety, and Workload: Experiment Findings', Submitted for Publication in the Human-Friendly Robotics 2024, HFR: 17th International Workshop on Human-Friendly Robotics (https://link.springer.com/book/9783031816871) Contributing partner: SUPSI</p>
4	<p>Conference Paper A. Kiourtis, A. Mavrogiorgou, N. Zafeiropoulos, K. Mavrogiorgos, A. Karabetian and D. Kyriazis, "UI/UX Sustainable Design: Best Practices for Applications CO2 Emissions Reduction," <i>2024 9th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech)</i>, Bol and Split, Croatia, 2024, pp. 01-06, doi: 10.23919/SpliTech61897.2024.10612495. Contributing partner: UPRC</p>
5	<p>Conference Paper Kiourtis et al., "XR5.0: Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for Industry 5.0," <i>2024 36th Conference of Open Innovations Association (FRUCT)</i>, Lappeenranta, Finland, 2024, pp. 314-323, doi: 10.23919/FRUCT64283.2024.10749931. Contributing partners: UPRC, INNOV-ACTS, UNP, UBI, IML, ATB , IPIA, GFT</p>
6	<p>Conference Paper Improving Collaborative Robotics: Insights On The Impact of Human Intention Prediction, submitted. Contributing partner: SUPSI</p>

4.3 Workshops, Webinars and Events

Workshops, webinars and events are vital in fostering collaboration and facilitating knowledge exchange. These activities can bring together stakeholders, including project partners, experts, policymakers, and

end-users, to come together and engage in targeted discussions, problem-solving exercises, and skill-building activities. As the project progresses into a more mature stage, partners will actively engage in an increasing number of workshops, webinars, events, and exhibitions. These activities will serve as key opportunities to present and promote the project's outcomes, demonstrating its achievements and impact to a broader audience. Currently, XR5.0 partners participated in the activities listed in Table 5.

Table 5 - Partners' participations and contributions in workshops and other events

Date	Partner	Country	Explanation of dissemination activity
June 12-14, 2024	SSF	Switzerland	From the 12th to 14th of June, 70+ participants from over 10 countries around the world gathered for an exceptional event organized in collaboration with UNIDO and Swiss CxO Forum (SCF).
October 24-25, 2024	EKSO	Italy	Pilot 3 Workshop, organized by EKSO on 24-25 October in Milan, Italy. The workshop was open to all partners, especially to the technical ones. Read more in the relevant post, found in the XR5.0 website here .
November 12-14, 2024	SSF & LNS	Switzerland	Internal Technical Meeting. The XR5.0 I Technical & Use Case Meeting was held in Bienne, 12-14 November, hosted by SSF & LNS.. The objective of the meeting was to see how the use cases work and saw what was the status of the technical stuff towards the II General Assembly.
October 29, 2024	TAP, IML	Portugal	Pilot 4 Workshop in Lisbon 29 Oct (Physical workshop) for a demo of the XR TAP training.
November 22, 2024	ATB	Germany	Presentation of the XR5.0 main objectives and activities to one of ATB's interest groups; 22/11/2024; Around 10 persons attended the workshop
November 29, 2024	INNOV	Greece	Lecture in Harokopio University ³ titled: "LLM Agents for Real-World Applications: The Case of Stock Analysis and Training Assistants in VR" The audience included 40 MSc students of the Institution (i.e. Harokopio University, Department of Informatics and Telematics). The lecture covered key aspects relevant to XR5.0, specifically focusing on the architectures and implementation of Large Language Models (LLMs) for industrial training applications in Virtual Reality environments. This lecture aligned closely with the project's objectives in advancing XR technologies for industrial applications.

³ <https://www.hua.gr/>

4.4 Future Planning (M13-M24) (January 2024-December 2024)

Table 6 below outlines the scientific publications (journals and conferences) planned by project partners through June 2025 to reach the identified target audiences. While this list serves as a guideline, it is subject to change, and some activities may not occur as initially anticipated. The XR5.0 project anticipates revising certain planned activities, such as substituting conference venues with alternative locations and adjusting the scope and content of specific activities. Any updates to these plans will be documented in the forthcoming WP7 deliverable, D7.2, scheduled for submission in December 2025 (M12).

Table 6-XR5.0 Plan for Scientific Publications (M13-M24) (Indicative List).

Indicative dates	Type of Publications	Publication Description	Partner
March 2025	Journal Publication	Evolution of Immersive Technologies: A literature review	UPRC
June 2025	Journal Publication	XR5.0 Applications in Industry 5.0 and beyond	UPRC
June 2025	Conference Publication	XR5.0 Architecture & Offerings to the EU XR Platform	UPRC
June 2025	Journal Publication	Anomaly detection using Computing Vision and AI for Industry 5.0	UPRC
March 2025	Journal Publication	Methodological Proposal for Co-Creation Processes in XR 5.0 Applications	IPIA
March 2025	Journal Publication	A Human-Centric Framework for Analyzing Human Factors in XR Applications for Industry 5.0	IPIA
Late 2025	Conference workshop /	Increased Effectiveness and Safety of Product Assembly and Repair Processes	SPACE
Early 2026	Book Chapter	A book chapter contribution to a collection on the ethical and legal aspects of AI and XR, using the XR5.0 project as a case study. The book is scheduled for publication in early 2026, with the chapter estimated to be finalized and accepted by June 2025.	CORCOM

Lists of relevant conferences offering publication opportunities for the project are regularly shared with all partners (see Table 7). These lists includes events that align closely with the project's objectives and target audiences.

Table 7- Indicative Conferences circulated among partners

Date	Conference	Deadline for submission of papers
TBA	Stereopsia 2025	TBA
April 9-11,2025	Laval Virtual 2025 - Call for Tech Talks	Become an exhibitor.
June 25-27, 2025	10th International XR - Metaverse	15 January 2025

June 17-20,2025	International Conference on eXtended Reality (XR Salento 2025)	Paper submission: February 28, 2025
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5. THE EU XR PROJECTS CLUSTER: AN INITIATIVE WITH XR5.0 IN A LEADING ROLE

During the project's first year, the XR5.0, following the dissemination KPIs, started creating an XR cluster with other projects relevant to XR. Thus, a cluster was created with several projects participating. Establishing a dedicated XR technology cluster, a collaborative initiative that brought together several projects working on Extended Reality (XR) solutions.

In the project's first year, XR5.0 focused on the dissemination KPIs and began to form an XR cluster by connecting with other relevant projects. This initiative led to the establishment of a dedicated XR technology cluster, where multiple projects collaborated on Extended Reality (XR) solutions.

5.1 Participating Projects

The XR5.0 project has established synergies with several notable projects (see Table 8) to enhance collaboration and innovation in the XR domain. The Table below displays the ten projects that make up the XR cluster.

Table 8-XR cluster projects.

XR Cluster	
	XR4ED (https://xr4ed.eu/) brings together the EdTech and XR communities to establish an European reference platform on learning and training with XR that will provide a central access point to existing solutions and contribute to a leading position for Europe in cutting-edge technologies for education.
	XR2Learn (https://xr2learn.eu/) aims to establish cross-border creation of human-centric XR applications in education. The project will deliver its one-stop shop platform, organised as a Digital Innovation Hub, for all actors involved in the XR based educational applications supply chain, aimed at enhancing training in manufacturing and distance learning scenarios.
	XR2Industry (https://xr2industry.eu/) is focused on data privacy, empowerment and industrial relevance. XR2Industry envisions an open platform. The creation of a European reference platform aiming to develop and prototype advanced interoperable XR solutions to solve common challenges encountered by the industry (in areas such as assembly, maintenance, remote operation, training, design, logistics, etc.), placing the wellbeing of workers at the centre of the production process.
	The augMENTOR (https://augmentor-project.eu/) project is developing a pedagogical framework that leverages emerging technologies and integrates them in education and training, through an open-access AI-boosted toolkit aiming to accelerate skills development. augMENTOR will deploy personalised learning profiles that consider students' personal characteristics, needs and preferences based on appropriately structured data that capture learning paths, ultimately addressing potential underlying educational difficulties and enabling students to reach their full potential.
	The main objective of MOTIVATE XR (https://motivatexr.eu/) is to create a world's leading XR collaborative authoring, publishing, and experiencing tool suite for training and assistance to industrial operations such as the assembly, manufacturing, maintenance, and dismantlement, of industrial goods.

	CORTEX2 (https://cortex2.eu/) envisions a world where remote collaboration is easy, efficient, and accessible for all. It aims to facilitate remote collaboration between workers through next-generation extended reality (XR) technology solutions across a wide range of industries and SMEs.
	HECOF (https://hecof.eu/) aims to revolutionize teaching in higher education through AI-driven personalized, adaptive learning. Focused on Chemical Engineering, it leverages digital data to enhance student assessment and learning methods. HECOF fosters ethical AI development and supports education sector reform, aligning with the Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027). It seeks to impact both academic and vocational training by promoting innovative digital teaching practices.
	MASTER (https://www.master-xr.eu/) enhances robotics training in manufacturing with its open XR platform. It integrates key functionalities, creating safe and flexible robotic environments with advanced interaction mechanisms. The project delivers rich training content and invites third-party contributions through two Open Calls.
	OPENVERSE (https://open-verse.eu/) is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA), funded under Horizon Europe programme. It's rooted in the ambition to elevate the European Union's landscape, responding to the global tech competition and fostering technological sovereignty.
	VOXReality (https://voxreality.eu/) is an initiative that aims to facilitate the convergence of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Computer Vision (CV) technologies in the Extended Reality (XR) field. VOXReality's goal is to conduct research and develop new AI models to drive future XR interactive experiences, and to deliver these models to the wider European market.

5.2 Joint Meetings of Clustered Projects

Monthly meetings are organized in order to coordinate the collaborations with other XR-focused projects and initiatives. As illustrated in Table 9, these monthly sessions facilitate structured planning and ensure cohesive dissemination efforts. Some of the key joint actions discussed in these meetings include cross-referencing projects on websites, boosting outreach through social media mentions, and leveraging email campaigns to highlight collective achievements and milestones. The possibility of producing a shared newsletter is also under exploration. This joint newsletter will offer a unified voice to promote innovations and developments across the network.

Beyond communication, these meetings lay the groundwork for impactful cluster webinars to engage specific audiences within the XR community. These webinars provide a platform for showcasing collaborative outcomes, sharing expertise, and addressing the interests of industry stakeholders, researchers, and potential end-users. The goal of this collaborative approach with similar efforts is to provide opportunities for sharing experiences, best practices, ideas, and expertise. A solid foundation for developing an enhanced pool of collective knowledge is provided by exchanging the experiences, knowledge, and viewpoints of the initiatives. Workshops, webinars, and seminars are some of the most prominent instances of collaborative activities. Furthermore, forming partnerships with additional related projects will increase the influence and scope of each project separately.

To facilitate the collaborative processes, a common Google Drive has been created to gather all the necessary information (see Figure 24).

Figure 24-Common repository of XR projects.

Table 9-Joint Meeting and Activities with Projects of the XR Cluster

Date	Projects	Discussion Points
7 March, 2024	XR4ED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-marketing strategy on social media • Planning a joint workshop or webinar for XR4ED and XR5.0
23 April, 2024	XR2Learn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross marketing actions (social media) • XR2Learn has created a community forum: https://forum.xr2learn-marketplace.eu/. XR5.0 will participate in this • A telco with XR4ED and XR2Learn will take place next months. • Community building • Create common publications/whitepapers
14 June, 2024	Motivate XR, Vox Reality, XR2Learn, XR4ED, XR2Industry, OPEN VERSE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scope of Collaboration (Webinars, Joint Workshops, Joint Publications, Standardisation, Community Building) • Initial Planning (e.g., Workshops/Webinars for September/October 2024) • Cross-marketing activities • Scientific activities like the production of white papers and scientific papers
July 5th, 2024	Cortex, Master, XR4ED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a common list for future events and explore the possibilities of having joint activities in future events • Webinars planning - A call for speakers where we could add speakers from our projects and participate. • Creation of common repository
August 8th, 2024	Cortex, Master, XR4ED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual’s webinar • Newsletters reach was discussed. CORTEX discussed about the LinkedIn newsletter • Approach new relevant projects • Discussions about posting on LinkedIn groups

September 16, 2024	Cortex, Master, XR4ED, XR2Learn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Suggestion for newsletter content: include general news on project domains ● Updates about the 1st webinar ● CORTEX2 expressed interest in participating in the cluster's second webinar ● MasterXR expressed interest in participating in the second cluster's webinar ● Next cluster's webinar in November. XR5.0 will update the cluster with more information
October 4th, 2024	Cortex, Master, XR4ED, XR2Learn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Updates about the 2nd webinar ● Suggestion for newsletter content: include general news on project domains ● Suggestion of creating a name of the XR cluster
November 1st, 2024	Cortex, Master, XR4ED, XR2Learn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Updates about the 2nd webinar ● Discussions about enhancing the XR cluster

5.3 Joint Webinars

During the project's first year, the XR5.0 dissemination team organised two webinars with the XR cluster (see Table 10). These webinars have been very successful, with high attendance; in particular, the first one was sold out.

5.3.1 1st Webinar: "The Ultimate Fusion: Extended Reality Meets Artificial Intelligence"

On September 12th, 2024, from 13:00 to 15:00 CET, the exclusive webinar "The Ultimate Fusion: Extended Reality Meets Artificial Intelligence" showcased the latest research and innovation at the intersection of Artificial Intelligence and Extended Reality (see Figure 25). The event had 100 participants registered, and 70 individuals attended. The webinar featured distinguished speakers from notable projects and initiatives, providing diverse insights into integrating AI and XR technologies. Discussions ranged from the convergence of these technologies to better understand human cognition to their use in teaching robotics, showcasing their transformative impact across various fields. Presenters shared their expertise and research outcomes, enriching the audience with valuable knowledge. Sessions included engaging discussions on the applications of XR and AI in industrial education, covering topics such as AI-driven virtual humans, innovative pedagogical frameworks, and more. The event underscored the potential of XR and AI to revolutionise industry and learning environments.

Detailed information about the 1st webinar, including the agenda, the presentations and the recording of the event can be found on the XR5.0 project website at: <https://xr50.eu/news/1st-xr-projects-cluster-webinar-titled-the-ultimate-fusion-extended-reality-meets-artificial-intelligence/>

5.3.2 2nd Webinar: "Virtual Visions: How XR is Reshaping Training Landscapes"

On November 5th, 2024, from 14:00 to 16:00 CET, the 2nd Webinar of the XR Projects Cluster, titled "Virtual Visions: How XR is Reshaping Training Landscapes", highlighted the latest advancements in Extended Reality and its transformative influence on professional training environments (see Figure 26). The webinar recorded the registration from 70 participants, with almost 40 individuals attending. The event brought together distinguished speakers each offering unique insights into applying XR technologies across various sectors. Presenters shared their expertise and research findings, providing participants with valuable knowledge and practical examples of XR's impact. The session concluded with an interactive discussion, allowing attendees to engage directly with the experts, ask questions, and delve into future trends shaping the XR landscape.

Detailed information about the 2nd webinar, including the agenda, the presentations and the recording of the event, can be found in the XR5.0 project website at: <https://xr50.eu/news/2nd-webinar-of-xr-projects-cluster-virtual-visions-how-xr-is-reshaping-training-landscapes-2/>

Table 10-Overview Information about the two Joint webinars of the XR Cluster

Webinar/ Date	Registered Participants	Attendees
“The Ultimate Fusion: Extended Reality Meets Artificial Intelligence”, September 12th, 2024, from 13:00 to 15:15 CET.	100	70
“Virtual Visions: How XR is Reshaping Training Landscapes,” November 5th, 2024, from 14:00 to 16:10 CET.	90	40

Figure 25-Social Media post - Recording of the 1st Clusters' webinar

Figure 26-Social Media post - Recording of the 2nd Clusters' webinar

5.4 Future Planning (M13-M24) (January 2025- December 2025)

The dissemination team is planning more webinars within the XR cluster, with the first one destined to occur during the first two months of 2025. The next steps for every webinar includes identifying

contributing projects and finding a suitable dates. Moreover, relevant visual for dissemination on social media is created, email campaigns are executed, and the event is disseminated through the different channels of the various projects. The topics of the 2025 webinars will span the areas of XR legal and regulatory issues, of XR standardization, as well as technological topics like tracking and devices for industrial XR environments. Furthermore, the monthly meetings with the projects of the XR cluster will continue towards with planning additional joint activities, including joint publications, joint face-to-face workshops, and joint standards and policy development efforts.

6. STAKEHOLDERS DATABASE

One of the key dissemination outcomes of XR5.0 is the project’s stakeholders’ database. This database aggregates contacts from various sources, including the project’s social media platforms (LinkedIn, X, YouTube, Facebook), email lists, webinars’ registrations, and more. The collected information includes names, email addresses, the platform through which the data is obtained, and additional details, such as country and professional categories. According to the KPI for the first year, the project aimed to gather 250 contacts in this database. Our work during the first year of the project has exceeded this target, as approximately 475 contacts have been added to the database at the time of writing this deliverable.

Figure 27 below presents the 20 most frequent countries of stakeholders’ contact in the database. The top three are Greece (105), Italy (36), and Portugal (31). Approximately 66 contacts are from academic partners (such as universities), while others come from different industrial sectors where XR is applied. The database primarily comprises records from the Technology and Software Development sector. Research and Academic professionals constitute the next largest group. In terms of professional roles, Project Managers and Marketing Professionals are the categories with the most members, with Creative Professionals and Business Management Professionals following thereafter. Regarding the channel through which the contacts were collected, as presented in Figure 28, most of them are from LinkedIn (358 records), followed by contacts from webinars (87 records) and from the X platform (29 records).

All data collected is securely stored and managed in compliance with GDPR regulation, including informed consent and minimal data collection practices.

Figure 27-Top 20 Stakeholders’ Countries Registered in the Stakeholders’ database.

Figure 28-Channels through which entries of the Stakeholders' Database have been collected.

7. STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES

7.1 Standardisation liaisons and methodology

XR5.0 partner TOG is responsible for leading standardisation liaisons and activities within the XR5.0 project. This task primarily focuses on standardisation, clustering, and policy-making activities related to the project. The work involves liaisons and participation with industrial associations (EFFRA, DAIRO, AIOTI), project clusters and initiatives (e.g., AI4Europe, AI4Manufacturing), national manufacturing initiatives (e.g., Platform Industrie 4.0, Productech, Industry 2025), as well as SDOs (IEEE, ISO, CEN/CENELEC, ETSI). The project will contribute insights into pre-normative activities based on whitepapers, presentations to meetings of the above-listed initiatives, as well as participation in joint meetings and workshops.

The XR5.0 project partners recognise the importance of standardisation as one of the cornerstones of the overall dissemination and exploitation strategy for XR5.0 aimed at achieving widespread take-up of project results for European I5.0 applications and services. The use of existing standards and activities to standardise project innovations will accelerate and amplify the exploitation of the project innovations by providing the following benefits:

- Wider dissemination of results – standards-setting organisations and communities surrounding standards have substantial participation from actors involved in related XR technologies – proposals by the XR5.0 partners to extend existing standards or introduce new standards represent well-focused dissemination actions towards industrial organisations, technology providers, and academia.
- Greater confidence by industry – organisations seeking to exploit the project’s XR systems development and personalisation technologies will have greater confidence in the project results if they are based on existing standards, and even more so when parts of the new project technologies are being adopted as new standards, as this conveys greater longevity and broader involvement by industry beyond the consortium partners, as well as a more transparent process for technology evolution.
- Interoperability of components – the publication of standards utilised in developing the XR5.0 solution and any proposed new standards provides the ability for third-parties that might develop XR-based applications and services to be incorporated within the XR5.0 ecosystem, providing additional benefits to XR application developers and opportunities for specialist component providers (e.g. augmented and virtual reality equipment vendors) to exploit the technologies developed in the project.
- Choice of technology suppliers for I5.0 stakeholders – the use of existing standards and the establishment of new standards based on the project technologies gives I5.0 stakeholders a greater choice of technology suppliers as other components can be easily incorporated into the XR5.0 framework for new applications and services, or other XR deployment environments beyond those validated in the project can be easily targeted, thereby avoiding lock-in to potentially proprietary technologies.

The use of standards and standardisation of project results therefore supports both the exploitation and dissemination strategies, and contributes towards achieving the industrial impacts targeted by the project. Standardisation liaisons and activities provide information about standards for use in the XR5.0-Reference Model, as well as knowledge of how XR5.0 aligns with European laws, acts, and directives (Table 11), especially in rapidly evolving technology areas such as AI and digital twins.

Table 11-Standardisation liaisons and activities.

Partners	Standards/Directive - Results Alignment	Contribution to XR5.0
CYENS, SUPSI	OpenXR i.e., Khronos Group open standard for access to VR/AR engines and devices including holographic devices and immersive VR devices	XR5.0 will use OpenXR for access to XR assets and devices as part of the UCs; It will propose extensions to the standard for interactions with Human-Centric XR-based DTs
TOG, UNP	Augmented Reality Framework from the ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG ARF)	XR5.0 will consider the ISG ARF in the specification of the XR5.0-Reference Model and will propose enhancements
IPIA, TOG	XR Safety Initiative (XRSI) Standards	Used in the XR5.0 co-creation to ensure safety/security
GFT, TOG	JTC 1/SC 42, AI Architecture: Standardised Architecture for BigData and AI Systems	XR extensions to this architecture will be provided as part of the XR5.0-ReferenceModel specification through DAIRO
COR, GFT	AI Act / AI Regulation: Proposal for regulating AI systems, as put forward by the EP and the Council of Europe	XR5.0 systems will be assessed against their compliance to the AI Act based on the level of their risk for the worker; Feedback from the risk assessment will be provided to policy makers
UPRC, INNOV	IEEE P2976 Standard (XAI): Standard specifying the properties of an XAI model	XR5.0 will consider this standard in the specification of requirements for the XAI models to be considered in the project
LXS, TOG	Open Standards for AI Model Interoperability: ONNX, OpenML, IEEE 2941-2021	XR5.0 will develop AI models based on these standards to facilitate their exchange, interoperability, and reuse across XR environments.
TOG, COR, IPIA	IEEE 7000 standards for ethical AI applications	XR5.0 will use IEEE 7000 based benchmarks

As contributions to extend existing standards and potentially propose new standards are expected to accelerate industry adoption of the XR5.0 person-centric and AI-based paradigm for XR applications, the consortium has established a methodology for the selection of standardisation targets that will be applied as the technology development and industry validation tasks are undertaken in the project and needed extensions to existing standards and possibly proposed new standards are identified. The methodology is summarised in the following sections.

7.1.1 Standards body selection

Process characteristics of standards bodies and the nature of their outputs play an important role in selecting the organisation that best fits the standardisation targets for the project. Key characteristics that will play a decisive role in the selection of the standards bodies to be targeted for adopting the project results are as follows:

The alignment of the standardisation goals of XR5.0 with the scope of the targeted organisation;
 The alignment of the methods, processes and principles applied by the targeted organisation with XR5.0 project objectives, as well as the standardisation results and impact being pursued;

- The lifespan of the XR5.0 project and the timing of deliverables with the agenda of the targeted standards organisation;
- The geographic scope of the impact XR5.0 is pursuing through its planned standardisation activities and targets;
- IPR rules and confidentiality policies of targeted standards bodies, as well as XR5.0 consortium partners' requirements;
- Membership rules and procedures for standards bodies and the possibilities for XR5.0 partners' input and proposals to be taken into account.

In cases where the project technologies intended for standardisation are extensions to existing standards, the first choice for the standards organisation or community to target becomes clear. However, in the mostly new technology areas developed within the project, significant consideration must be given in the selection of the standards organisation or community to be targeted.

7.1.2 Timing

Standardisation processes are largely market-driven and usually start when market actors have identified the need to initiate a process of capturing user, industrial or functional requirements for what is to become a new or an improved specification or standard. When putting forward project results for standardisation, it is important to ensure that the challenge or area addressed is actually on the agenda of the targeted standards body, and that there is sufficient critical mass among the target standards body's members to at least support if not contribute to the process of finalising the specification or reference technology from the XR5.0 project.

If this is not the case, additional efforts to build consensus or engage constituents may be necessary. However, if there is a belief that this situation can be changed within a reasonable timeframe, it might be advisable for XR5.0 to explore alternative organizations that have agendas more aligned with the standardization objectives of the XR5.0 project.

7.1.3 Technology focus area

Finding the standards body best covering the scope of XR5.0 technologies may seem a relatively easy part of the selection process. Nevertheless, it can be complicated to point out a single organisation because in some cases several standards bodies are addressing the specific standardisation area being targeted. In particular, multiple initiatives are underway for standardisation of various aspects of AI and digital twins and many existing standards addressing virtual and augmented reality technologies. Consequently, it may be necessary to define in much more detail the specifics of the envisaged results, which may not always be possible in the early to middle stages of the project.

Project results may be relevant to several standards bodies, but project resources may not be sufficient to interface with all of them. The specific focus areas are best selected after the first industry validations in the project have been completed as this will provide greater assurance that XR5.0 will be able to pursue its standardisation goals and the inputs collected from industrial partners can be used to motivate proposed adoption of project results as new industry standards.

7.1.4 Open standardisation processes

There are a number of commonalities between processes adopted by most organisations that have proven to be essential to conducting voluntary, open, and market-driven standardisation processes. The following criteria have therefore been established by XR5.0 in selecting the target standards bodies:

- Specifications or standards are essentially the result of consensus between parties involved, and participation of all relevant stakeholders should be sufficiently ensured, e.g. by validating draft specifications through a public review process;
- Standardisation activities are carried out through what are essentially public processes; although

work may normally be done by expert committees, other interested parties should have the opportunity to become involved;

- Approved drafts of standards and specifications are formally ratified by the members of the standards organisation, and subsequently published;
- Standards produced by an organisation are available to all interested parties either free of charge, or licensable on FRaND⁴ terms;
- Interoperability between various implementations is verified, either as part of the standardisation process or through a process of self-certification, installed by the parties involved, and its maintenance is embedded in the evolutionary processes of the standard.

The final criteria of verification are often the most challenging as many standards organisations do not establish procedures for the verification of products as being conformant to their standards. However, as project partner TOG operates certification programmes for its own and many other standards organisations, a shortcoming in this area by a candidate standards organisation may not be grounds for disqualification as TOG has the ability to put in place a certification programme for new or extended standards based on XR5.0 project results.

7.1.5 Confidentiality and intellectual property

Standards organisations do not always have the same rules with respect to confidentiality and intellectual property rights (IPR). While there are organisations that require their members and/or participants to submit their contributions and technologies or specifications for free (i.e. without obligations for users of this technology to pay license fees), other organisations may work under an IPR regime offering their contributors opportunities for exploiting standardised technology through licensing.

As part of the selection process, the IPR regime of the targeted standards organisations will be considered by XR5.0 partners, as well as their confidentiality policies, to verify it is aligned with project partners' requirements.

7.1.6 Geographic focus areas

Generally speaking, XR5.0 is pursuing standardisation of results at a global level in support of the I5.0. This will maximise exposure of project innovations to industry and consequently widen dissemination opportunities. In addition, it will help to prevent competing regional standards from emerging, which may cause barriers to trade for European XR platform providers and equipment vendors. However, some specific criteria for pursuing standardisation targets at a regional level should also be considered:

- Taking specific national or regional legislative or product/services requirements into account;
- Project partners that are particularly well embedded in national or regional standardisation organisations or processes;
- Resources needed for national or regional standardisation processes can be considerably lower and can often influence broader European standards.

Regional and global standardisation systems in some technologies are complementary, and several standards bodies have arrangements in place for addressing this, for example, in the area of national and EU-level security standards. Nevertheless, cooperation and exchange between globally and regionally orientated standards organisations is mostly organised on an ad-hoc basis for many technology areas.

7.1.7 Membership of standards bodies

Most standards bodies offer their membership to a variety of organisations, encompassing individual companies, non-profit organisations, institutions, governmental bodies, etc. although some formal standards bodies restrict membership to nationally appointed representatives. Although research projects are usually not excluded from membership, there can be several reasons (e.g. the financial consequences, or the limitations of a project's lifespan) for not applying for membership as a project. There are also some standards organisations where membership is not strictly necessary for participating in at least part of the

⁴ Fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory

standardisation process, while taking part in the decision making process usually does require membership. Some alternatives in case direct membership is not feasible are identified as follows:

- Participate through the membership of one of the project’s consortium partners;
- Apply for an observer status or temporary membership that is offered by some standards bodies or industry consortia;
- Utilise public events (e.g. seminars, conferences, etc.) and forums that are sometimes organised by standards organisations for making contributions;
- Submit results through other standards organisations that are able to participate in the activities of the specific standards body a project intends to target (e.g. TOG has cross-membership agreements with several other standards organisations).
- Some standards bodies are willing to establish low or unfunded partnerships with EU-funded projects where the envisaged research is closely aligned with the interests of the organisation.

Considerations concerning membership in terms of costs, required representation for discussions and consensus building, and ability to influence outcomes and decision-making have been included in the selection process of standards organisations to be targeted by the XR5.0 project.

7.2 Initial technology candidates and target standards bodies

Table 12 lists the current collaborations with standards organisations and communities in topics related to the project technology innovations. These represent an initial set of candidate targets for potential extensions to existing standards that will potentially be expanded as the technology development and industry validation tasks are carried out in the project. The set of candidates will eventually be prioritised by the project partners and a subset selected for specific actions to be taken towards standardisation by consortium partners in collaboration with XR5.0 standardisation lead.

Table 12 –Envisaged Collaboration with SDOs

SDO/ Association Liaisons/ Working Group	Scope of Liaison / Collaboration	Technical Lead
IEEE Standards Association, the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)	W3C standards will be considered in the design and development of the XR5.0 user interfaces	SPACE
Virtual Reality Industry Forum (VRIF)	XR5.0 will consult VRIF guidelines for video interfaces	SPACE
RAMI, Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0 ⁵	RAMI4.0 will be considered as a background reference model for the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI
IIRA Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (https://www.iiconsortium.org/iira/)	IIRA will be also among the background reference architectures that will be used to drive the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI
LASFA, LASim Smart Factory ⁶	LASFA will be also among the background reference architectures that will be used to drive the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI

⁵ <https://www.isa.org/intech-home/2019/march-april/features/rami-4-0-reference-architectural-model-for-industr>

⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360835221001455#b0355>

SDO/ Association Liaisons/ Working Group	Scope of Liaison / Collaboration	Technical Lead
SITAM, Stuttgart IT-Architecture for Manufacturing ⁷ and IVRAM, Industrial Value Chain Reference Architecture ⁸	SITAM and IVRAM will be also among the background reference architectures that will be used to drive the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI
Archimate for architecture design (https://www.archimatetool.com/)	For system engineering, we will use, adapt, and possibly extend aspects of this standard	UBI
Elements of TOGAF for architecture design (https://www.opengroup.org/togaf)	For system engineering, we will use, adapt, and possibly extend aspects of this standard	UBI
Elements of EIRA for interoperability (https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/european-interoperability-reference-architecture-eira)	For system engineering, we will use, adapt, and possibly extend aspects of this standard	UBI

The XR5.0 standardisation lead maintains also close links and liaisons with several other XR5.0 related SDOs, including the Digital Twin Consortium (DTC), the Object Management Group (OMG), IEEE, ETSI, CEN/CENELEC, ISO/CD TS 81001-2-1 (Health software and health IT systems safety, effectiveness and security – new standards for ensuring the safety of connected embedded devices), ISO/IEC 20243-2:2023: Open trusted technology provider standard; the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and the International Committee for Information Technology Standards (INCITS). As part of the implementation of the standardisation task of the project, these links may be exploited to share/contribute XR5.0 outcomes once they become available. As the technology developments in the project progress, the partners in collaboration with TOG will be identifying the most appropriate of these SDOs to target with respect to the expected outcomes of XR5.0. Updated information and planning will be reported in the scope of deliverable D7.3.

In preparation for project actions aimed at standardization, XR5.0 partners have developed a set of common steps to achieve industry standardization of selected project outcomes. The timing and actions to be taken will vary depending on the project technology, its maturity, and the standardisation body or community being targeted. The steps envisioned to be taken for each project technology targeted for standardisation are the following:

- **Submission preparation** – preparing the XR5.0 research and development results as a specification or proposal suitable for submission to the standards body or community to support the process of industry review and comment.
- **Constituency building** – partners identify various influential constituencies that will have an opinion or position with regard to the XR5.0 submission and will liaise them to understand their interests and positions and to solicit their support.
- **Consensus building** – organising meetings and briefings with those individuals or organisations that are important for the decision-making within a standards organisation or community.
- **Conflict resolution** – addressing questions, challenges, and alternative approaches from others outside the project consortium concerning the XR5.0 submission that has been forwarded to the targeted standards organisation or community for review and comment.
- **Acceptance** – the action by the standards community of recognising the XR5.0 specification as being an

⁷ https://www.ipvs.uni-stuttgart.de/departments/as/downloadgallery_as/groegech/Kassner_Stuttgart_IT_Architecture_for_Manufacturing.pdf

⁸ (https://docs.iv-i.org/doc_161208_Industrial_Value_Chain_Reference_Architecture.pdf)

extension to an existing portfolio of specifications and technologies, or as a new industry reference standard.

Each of the project technologies eventually selected for standardisation will progress through each of the standardisation steps through actions taken by the project partners. Some of the steps may not be completed until after the project is finalised due either to the maturity of the technology results, or the time required by the targeted standards body or community to complete their required consensus and publication procedures.

7.3 Liaisons with and Contributions to Industrial Associations

The EU partners will liaise with industrial associations at the European level in order to contribute to their activities based on XR5.0 results. The scope of the contributions will include participation in events and meetings organized by the associations, preparation of joint papers or contribution to whitepapers of the associations, as well as collaboration with other members around the XR5.0 technologies and use cases. Moreover, the project will exploit the opportunities for liaising and collaborating with associations of the Swiss Manufacturing/Industry 5.0 ecosystem, thanks to the participation of the Associated (Swiss) partners in the XR5.0 consortium. For example, SSF will promote the project’s outcomes to its partners and members of its ecosystem in Switzerland (i.e., to approx. 3000 persons per year). Furthermore, SSF will establish liaisons and exchanges with clusters and initiatives in 3 other sectors: the Swiss Healthtech Center, the Swiss Battery Technology Center, and the Swiss Advanced Manufacturing Center. Also, SSF will engage with associations like the Lions Club and Industrie 2025. Moreover, LNS is part of the Swissmem association, which has more than 1250 members in the mechanical and electrical engineering industries. It will therefore promote XR5.0 in this community.

Table 13 provides a list of collaborations with industrial associations that will be pursued by the partners. It is important to note that this list is not exhaustive and will undergo continuous updates and improvements as the XR5.0 project progresses and reaches higher levels of maturity.

Table 13 – Liaisons and Envisaged Collaboration with Industrial Associations

Industrial Association / Working Group	Scope of Collaboration	Partners
Data AI and Robotics (DAIRO)	Sharing of information about the XR5.0 architectures and its alignment to DAIRO (and BDVA) reference models; Participation in DAIRO organized/supported events like the Data Week and the EBDVF	GFT, UPRC
Alliance for IoT Innovation (AIOTI)	Participation in AIOTI sponsored events (e.g., IoT Week); Contribution to the AIOTI WG11 (IoT in Manufacturing) whitepapers/documents based on the use of XR in manufacturing	UNP,
European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA)	Participation in EFFRA events, project clusters and exhibitions	UNP, SUPSI, NOVA
Energetics Consortium – standards for oil/gas	TOG hosted SDO groupings that appear to be related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures.	TOG

energy production companies		
Exploration, Mining, Metals & Minerals Forum	TOG hosted SDO groupings that appear to be related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures as the focus of the forum is on enterprise architecture standards and reference models for the exploration, mining, metals, and minerals industries	TOG
Commercial Aviation Working Group – Commercial Aviation Reference Architecture	TOG hosted SDO groupings that appear to be related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures.	TOG
IT4IT Forum – Reference Architecture for managing the operations of IT in enterprise and government organisations	TOG hosted SDO groupings that appear to be related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures.	TOG
Enterprise Architecture Forum – TOGAF enterprise architecture methodology with over 100K certified IT architects around the world	TOG hosted SDO groupings addressing industry IT architecture methods and tools.	TOG
ArchiMate Forum – industry standard modelling language for enterprise architecture	TOG hosted SDO groupings addressing industry IT architecture methods and tools.	TOG
AITI Associazione Industrie Ticinesi, AGIRE, and Other EU initiatives that have AI in Industry 5.0 aspects (Circular Twain, BetterFactory, CIRCULOOS; KITT4SME, etc.)	Sharing of experience and results regarding AI and XR use cases in manufacturing; Joint meetings/workshops; Best practice sharing regarding the development of AI-based Digital Twins	SUPSI, NOVA

In-line with the DoA, the project will also establish liaisons with industrial associations at the National Level, such as Platform Industrie 4.0 in Germany (ATB, KUKA) and ProduTech in Portugal (UNP, IPIA). The primary goal of these collaborations will be to raise awareness about XR5.0 and engage stakeholders at the national level.

8. CONCLUSION

This deliverable outlines the dissemination and communication activities undertaken by the XR5.0 project during the first year of the project's lifetime. It has detailed the main dissemination and communication achievements of the project, including:

- The establishment of the project's brand image and the creation of relevant branding materials.
- The setup of the project's presence in social media, in channels like LinkedIn, X, Facebook and YouTube.
- The publication of regular posts about the project's results through all the different social media platforms where the project's has presence, with emphasis on LinkedIn as XR5.0 primary social media channel.
- The production and dispatch of four editions of the project's newsletter.
- The production of a continuous flow of blog posts that illustrate different aspects of the project's work and elaborate on the individual partners' contributions to the project.
- The publication of the project's results in scientific journals, conferences and magazines.
- The participation of the partners' in different workshops and events, where selected outcomes of the project were presented and/or demonstrated.
- The establishment of strong and effective collaborative links with other projects, which led to the formation of a cluster of EU-funded XR projects with XR5.0 in a leading role. XR5.0 led the organization of two joint webinars with cluster projects, while more webinars and other collaborative activities are planned for the second year of the project's lifetime.
- The creation and maintenance of a stakeholders' database, which consolidates the contacts of and within people and organisations that have engaged with the project's results.
- The establishment of standardization-related liaisons to prepare for the project's pre-standardization and policy development activities.

Overall, the dissemination and communication activities of the project have evolved in-line with the density of the scientific and technological development work of the project and in-line with the dissemination plans and KPIs listed in the DoA. The dissemination efforts of the project during the first year have ensured substantial visibility, accessibility, and promotion of the XR5.0 project. All partners demonstrated strong alignment and commitment in the development and execution of the dissemination and communication plans, yet some of the partners' dissemination work will translate to tangible achievements (e.g., publications) during the next year of the project.

During 2025, the focus of the dissemination activities will shift towards producing more publications (including whitepapers), as well as towards intensifying the partners' participation in workshops, webinars, and events that will enable them to showcase project outcomes and engage more stakeholders. Nevertheless, the project partners are committed to continuing and sustaining successful activities that were carried out during the first year of the project, such as the XR clustering activities. The activities of the next year will be reported in the next deliverable of WP7 (D7.3), which is due in December 2025 (M14) and will be an updated report on the implemented dissemination and communication activities of XR5.0.

ANNEX I: XR5.0 ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE PARTNERS' WEB SITES

Table 14- XR5.0 Announcements.

Placement	Quotation
<p>Innov – Acts website</p>	
<p>CYENS website</p>	<p>XR5.0</p>
<p>SYNELIXIS website</p>	
<p>Technet.com</p>	

<p>Kiosquedaaviacao.pt</p>	<p>INSTITUTO PIAGET E TAP JUNTOS PARA REVOLUCIONAR A MANUTENÇÃO AERONÁUTICA COM IA E REALIDADE AUMENTADA</p> <p>Nacional 23 Novembro, 2024</p>
<p>Publico.pt</p>	<p>EXCLUSIVO INTELIGÊNCIA ARTIFICIAL</p> <p>Ansiedade ao executar uma tarefa no trabalho? E se IA lhe dissesse o que fazer?</p> <p>O projecto XR5.0 tem mais de 20 parceiros, incluindo a TAP. Orçamentado em mais de dez milhões de euros, está a ser liderado por um consórcio europeu do qual faz parte o Instituto Piaget.</p> <p>Filipa Almeida Mendes 21 de Novembro de 2024, 7:11</p>
<p>LNS website</p>	
<p>CORCOM website</p>	<p>CORCOM</p> <p>Home About Us Team Services Publications News Contact</p> <p>CORCOM kicks-off the XR5.0 Research and Innovation Action on human-centric, AI-enabled XR applications for Industry 5.0</p>
<p>oculavis website</p>	<p>XR5.0 oculavis</p> <p>Transforming Industrial Maintenance with XR Applications</p>

<p>SCHMIDT + HAENSCH website</p>	<p>Laboratory Equipment Maintenance</p> <p>Transforming Maintenance with XR Technologies: SCHMIDT + HAENSCH's Role in the XR5.0 Project</p>
<p>UBITECH website</p>	<p>UBITECH kicks off the XR5.0 Research and Innovation Action on human-centric, AI-enabled XR applications for Industry 5.0</p> <p>UBITECH participates at the kick-off meeting hosted by GFT (February 20 & 21, 2024) in Milan, Italy of the XR5.0: "Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era" Innovation Action, officially started on January 1st, 2024. The project is funded by the European Commission (Grant Agreement No. 101135209) and spans on the period January 2024 – December 2026. XR5.0 will build, demonstrate, and validate a novel Person-Centric and AI-based XR paradigm that will be tailored to the requirements and nature of I5.0 applications. In this direction, the project will specify structuring principles and blueprints for using XR in I5.0 applications with emphasis on the development of innovative "XR-made-in-Europe" technology that blends with human-centric manufacturing technologies and adheres to European values.</p>
<p>CORCOM website</p>	<p>CORCOM joins EU Horizon project on Extended Realities (XR)</p> <p>October 28, 2023 AI, data protection, data security, EU projects, GDPR, Industry 5.0, privacy, VR, XR</p> <p>CORCOM just received a new grant from the EU Commission to join the XR5.0 Horizon project. The project aims to create a person-centric and AI-based Extended Reality (XR) paradigm tailored for Industry 5.0 applications. It focuses on the integration of "XR-made-in-Europe" technology with human-centric manufacturing principles in line with European values. The project leverages human-centered digital twins and advanced AI paradigms to offer ergonomic and personalized training via a cloud-based XR platform. XR5.0 is developing six high-TRL pilot applications in areas such as AI-based product design and workers' training, all of which will be integrated into the EU XR platform and demonstrated in real-world manufacturing environments. The initiative is also fostering a community of stakeholders to ensure the sustainability and broader adoption of its innovative solutions, positioning the technologies for immediate commercialization. CORCOM will oversee all the legal and ethical aspects of the project.</p>
<p>Aktuelles website</p>	<p>XR5.0 Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era</p> <p>1. January 2024 escribano 0 Comments</p> <p>We proudly announce the the launch of our new project, XR5.0 (Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era – GA 101135209), starting on the first of January 2024 with 24 other partners.</p> <p>The project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Commission's research framework programme Horizon 2020, under the focus area "Emerging enabling technologies".</p>

<p>ATB website</p>	<p>The screenshot shows the ATB website with a blue navigation bar containing 'Home', 'Competencies / Research', 'Projects', 'References', 'News', and 'Contact'. The main content area features the 'XR5.0' logo in blue and purple. Below the logo, the text describes the project's goal to build, demonstrate, and validate a novel Person-Centric and AI-based XR paradigm for IS.0 applications, emphasizing innovative 'XR-made-in-Europe' technology and adherence to European values. It details the integration of human-centred digital twins (DTs) and advanced AI paradigms like explainable AI (XAI), Active Learning (AL), Generative AI (GenAI), and neurosymbolic learning. The project aims to develop a cloud-based XR training platform for Operator 5.0 applications, enabling ergonomic and personalized training of industrial workers. It also mentions the development of six (6) novel high-TRL pilot applications in areas like AI-based product design, remote and intelligent maintenance of assets, workers' training, support in product assembly, and guidance and instructions for troubleshooting. The applications will be integrated into the EU XR platform.</p>
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ANNEX II: SAMPLE POSTS BY XR5.0 PROJECT MEMBERS AND THIRD PARTIES

Figure 29 – XR5.0 Post from Consortium Member (8000+ impressions)

ANNEX III: XR5.0 (PUBLISHED) BLOG POSTS (M1-M12) (JAN 24 – DEC 24)

N0.	Visual	Blog Title - Linkable	LinkedIn Impressions (until November 2024)	Publication Date	Partner
1		Extended Reality (XR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) Integration: Five Industrial Cases you need to know	735	30/03/2024	INNOV
2		Personalizing XR Applications and Human-Robot Interaction with Digital Twins	1,154	03/04/2024	SUPSI
3		Empowering Industry 5.0: Unleashing Human-Centered Innovation with XR5.0	467	18/04/2024	IPIA

4		XR4ED and XR5.0 EU Projects: Synergies for Revolutionizing Training and Education with Made-in-Europe XR Solutions	742	17/04/2024	CYENS
5		Ethical Management and Regulatory Compliance Framework	205	16/05/2024	COR
6		Empowering Industrial Training: XR5.0's Role in Revolutionizing Workforce Education	456	28/05/2024	SSF
7		Transforming Industrial Maintenance with XR Applications	890	03/06/2024	OCU

8	<p>Blog</p> <p>How LeanXcale can solve the major challenges of data management for XR applications</p>	How LeanXcale can solve the major challenges of data management for XR applications	331	28/06/2024	LXS
9	<p>Blog</p> <p>Standards-based XR Architectures for Industrial use Cases</p>	Standards-based XR Architectures for Industrial Use Cases	969	02/07/2024	UBI
10	<p>Blog</p> <p>Revolutionizing Remote Assistance with Extended Reality for Virtual and Real Commissioning Automation Solutions</p>	Revolutionizing Remote Assistance with Xtended Reality for Virtual and Real Commissioning Automation Solutions	542	05/09/2024	KUKA
11	<p>Blog</p> <p>Extended Reality-Based Training in the Industry 5.0 Era</p>	Extended Reality-Based Training in the Industry 5.0 Era	445	09/09/2024	IML

12	<p>Blog</p> <p>XR Standards Landscape</p>	XR Standards Landscape	350	09/09/2024	TOG
13	<p>Blog</p> <p>Integrating Edge Devices with XR Environments for Personalized Training and Repairs Using Unity</p>	Integrating Edge Devices with XR Environments for Personalized Training and Repairs Using Unity	433	27/09/2024	SPACE
14	<p>Blog</p> <p>Enhancing XR5.0: Orchestration pipelines for smarter VR/AR solutions</p>	Enhancing XR5.0: Orchestration pipelines for smarter VR/AR solutions	652	14/10/2024	SIE
15	<p>Blog</p> <p>"Experience the Future: Tailored Training for Industrial Workers at EKSO 15.0"</p>	Experience the Future: Tailored Training for Industrial Workers at EKSO 15.0	285	21/10/2024	EKSO

<p>16</p>		<p>XR5.0 Pilot Preparation Meeting – tackle challenges and optimize the project’s strategies for the best outcomes.</p>	<p>402</p>	<p>11/11/2024</p>	<p>EKSO</p>
<p>17</p>		<p>Transforming Laboratory Instruments Maintenance with XR Technologies: SCHMIDT + HAENSCH's Role in the XR5.0 Project</p>	<p>171</p>	<p>19/11/2024</p>	<p>SH</p>
<p>18</p>		<p>Enhancing Aircraft Maintenance Training with AI-Powered XR Environments</p>	<p>288</p>	<p>19/11/2024</p>	<p>IML</p>
<p>19</p>		<p>The Role of an XR Streaming Platform for Industrial Training: Exploring Hololight Hub in XR5.0</p>	<p>235</p>	<p>29/11/2024</p>	<p>HOLO</p>

ANNEX IV: AGENDAS OF CLUSTER WEBINARS

*1st Webinar of XR Projects Cluster***“The Ultimate Fusion: Extended Reality Meets Artificial Intelligence”***September, 12th, 2024**13:00-15:00 CET***Agenda**

13:00 - 13:05	Introduction to the Cluster and the Webinar
	<i>XR & AI in Industrial Applications</i>
13:05 - 13:20	<i>“Virtual agents: the convergence of AI & XR to characterize human cognition”</i> Prof. Mariano Alcañiz Raya, XR2Industry Project
13:20 - 13:35	<i>“XR5.0: AI/LLMs & XR Integration for Industry 5.0 Applications”</i> John Soldatos, XR5.0 Project
13:35 - 13:50	<i>“MASTER: Leveraging XR and AI in teaching and training of robotics”</i> Panagiotis Karagiannis (CCed), MASTER Project
13:50 - 14:05	<i>“AI Meets XR: Motivate XR and VoxReality Approaches”</i> Nikolaos Achilleopoulos, Motivate XR Project and VoxReality Project
14:05 - 14:15	Short Break
	<i>XR & AI in Industrial Applications in Education</i>
14:15 - 14:30	<i>“AI virtual humans for XR education”</i> Fotis Liarokapis and Nuria Pelechano, XR4ED Project
14:30 - 14:45	<i>“augMENTOR project is this: Integrating Emerging Technologies in Education: Introducing the Innovative PeDeMET Pedagogical Framework”</i> Vassilis Komis and Andromachi Filippidi, augMENTOR project
14:45 - 15:00	Open Discussion – Questions & Answers

2nd Webinar of XR Projects Cluster

“Virtual Visions: How XR is Reshaping Training Landscapes”

05 November 2024, 14:00-16:10 CET

Meeting Registration Link: <https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/virtual-visions-how-xr-is-reshaping-training-landscapes-tickets-1039870258937?aff=oddtcreator>

Agenda

14:00 - 14:05 (5')	<i>“Introduction to the Cluster and the Webinar” John Soldatos, XR5.0 Project</i>
14:05 - 14:25 (20')	<i>“XR-enhanced training in industrial applications for collaborative robotics” Aleksander Burkiewicz, OpenVerse Project</i>
14:25 - 14:45 (20')	<i>“Reality-embedded learning in astronaut training - with CARATE” Prof Fridolin Wild, XR2Learn</i>
14:45 - 15:15 (20')	<i>“How does AR technology need to look like to get accepted by users?” Timon Binder, CTO and Co-Founder, Almer Technologies, XR5.0 Project</i>
15:15 - 15:35 (20')	<i>“Blending of XR Tech in learning methods” Jesus Rosel, MASTER Project</i>
15:35 - 15:55	<i>“Reality-based Learning in Virtual Reality for Industrial Training” Zakaria Oubbéa, CORTEX² project</i>
15:55 - 16:10 (20')	Open Discussion – Questions & Answers